

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19711500

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY ON THE DECENTRALIZATION OF POPULATION ADMINISTRATION-(A STUDY ON IMPROVING PUBLIC SERVICES AT THE BANDUNG REGENCY POPULATION AND CIVIL REGISTRATION OFFICE IN 2024)

Yudi Heryana^{1*}, Nandang Alamsah Deliarnoor² and Novie Indrawati Sagita³

¹Doctoral Student of Government Sciences, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Padjadjaran University.
Email: yudi22002@ymail.unpad.ac.id

^{2,3}Department of Government Sciences, Faculty of Social and Political Science, Padjadjaran University,
yudi22002@ymail.unpad.ac.id

Received: 05/03/2026
Accepted: 09/04/2026

Corresponding Author: Yudi Heryana
(yudi22002@gmail.unpad.ac.id)

ABSTRACT

The policy of decentralizing Population Administration Affairs has relegated the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil) to the role of a mere service provider, resulting in suboptimal Population Administration Services due to its limited authority. This study employs the framework proposed by Cheema and Rondinelli (1983), which encompasses: environmental conditions, inter-organizational relationships, resources, and characteristics of implementing agencies. This study employs a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach, positioning the researcher as the primary instrument. Data sources were obtained from agencies and service users, and data collection was conducted through observation, interviews, and document analysis. The collected data was processed through the following stages: data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The results of this study indicate that environmental conditions are constrained by limited authority and inadequate physical infrastructure. Inter-organizational relations are constrained by inconsistencies in the mapping of functions based on regulations and the lack of a structure for implementing service units as mandated by Law No. 24 of 2013. Regarding resource availability, constraints persist due to limited human resources. In the implementation of the Population Administration Decentralization policy, the characteristics of implementing institutions – specifically regarding the skills and commitment of implementers – need to be improved. The conclusion regarding the implementation of the Population Administration Decentralization policy in Bandung Regency is that there are constraints related to limited regional authority, limited supporting service infrastructure, limited human resources, and the commitment of implementing elements that need to be improved. The suggested concept and novelty of this study is adaptive decentralization, taking into account efficiency, accountability, externalities, and national strategic interests, which should be further tested in future government studies.

KEYWORDS: Policy Implementation, Public Services, Delegation of Authority, Population Administration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Decentralization in public services plays a crucial role in improving quality and efficiency. In the context of Population Administration (Adminduk), decentralization enables local governments to manage administrative services more effectively, allowing the public to access services more quickly and efficiently while reducing cumbersome bureaucracy. On the other hand, Law No. 23 of 2006 and its implementing regulations have designated Population Administration as a strategic government matter because it involves the fulfillment of every citizen's fundamental right and the management of highly confidential personal data. In other words, Population Administration is not merely a mandatory basic service but serves as the foundation for all public services.

According to a report by the Director of Population Registration and Civil Registration (Tayipriyono, 2024), of Indonesia's total population of 280.725.428 people registered in the Population Administration Information System (SIAK), 201.145.858 people—or 96,47%—have been registered. This means there is still work to be done to ensure that all Indonesian citizens are recognized and their residency status is protected, particularly for those living in remote and hard-to-reach areas. This situation was confirmed by the Directorate General of Population and Civil Registration of the Ministry of Home Affairs, where the implementation of population administration still faces various challenges, including: very limited budgets from the Regional Budget (APBD) and no further support from the State Budget (APBN) for population administration services in the regions; inadequate facilities and infrastructure (aging infrastructure and limited recording equipment); 60% of technical service staff are non-civil servants; the functional positions within the Population and Civil Registration Office (Database Administrator and SIAK Operator) have not yet been fully implemented; and there are still regions that have not provided additional funding to the Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*).

The issuance of birth certificates is also a problem. Public awareness of the importance of birth certificates remains low, with many people only applying for them when they are urgently needed to meet educational requirements. The rate of birth certificate ownership among residents aged 0–17 in Bandung Regency in 2024 was 1.039.663 out of a total population of 0–17-year-olds of 1.142.253 (Ministry of Home Affairs Population Control, Family Planning, Women's Empowerment, and Child Protection

Agency/DKB Kemendagri, 2nd Semester, 2024). Meanwhile, according to data from the Population Control, Family Planning, Women's Empowerment, and Child Protection Agency (P2KBP3A) of Bandung Regency, during 2024, out of the numerous underage marriages that occurred in Bandung Regency, approximately 1.069 men and women applied for marriage dispensations at the Soreang Religious Court in Bandung Regency. The total issuance of marriage certificates by the Population and Civil Registration Office throughout 2024 was recorded at only 71,74% of the total number of certificates required.

The implementation of population administration in Bandung Regency also faces technical challenges related to service infrastructure, including service buildings, operational vehicles,

biometric equipment, internet networks, and servers. Furthermore, in terms of human resources, vacancies may arise in functional positions. Based on Article 12 of Minister of PAN-RB Regulation No. 1 of 2023 concerning Functional Positions, the appointment of civil servants to Functional Positions may be carried out through initial appointment, transfer from another position, reassignment, and promotion. However, the technical implementation regulations have not yet been issued, so the vacancies in question cannot yet be filled.

The transition of the regulatory framework for civil registration to Law No. 23 of 2006 also impacted the structure of the implementing agencies responsible for delivering services. Under this regulation, civil registration services are to be provided, in part, by Technical Implementation Units/UPTs. Based on observations, the Bandung Regency Government has not established UPTs as mandated by law, resulting in the processing of service requests being concentrated within the department, which has limited resources.

This situation presents an interesting topic for research into why the delivery of Population Administration Services in Bandung Regency has not yet been optimal, as well as the factors influencing the success of Population Administration policy implementation in Bandung Regency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Implementation Of Decentralization Policy

As an effective mechanism for carrying out governmental functions, decentralization has several success determinants that must be considered. Cheema and Rondinelli (1983:27) outline the key factors for the success of decentralization policies, namely environmental conditions;

interorganizational relationships; resources for policy and program implementation; and the characteristics of implementing agencies.

Environmental conditions have a significant impact on both the organization as a whole and the bureaucracy in particular. Simply put, the delegation of authority must take into account the capacity of the party receiving the authority and clearly and consistently define their duties and responsibilities. The characteristics of the implementing organization are a key factor determining the success of policy execution, as implementation performance is heavily influenced by the quality of the internal of the agency serving as the spearhead of the policy's implementation (Prendergast et al., 2017). An outstanding organization is underpinned by the quality of its personnel; therefore, the organization must establish work and performance management systems capable of optimizing the potential of every employee. Sub-factors of the characteristics of implementing organizations include:

- **Technical And Managerial Capacity of Implementers**

The quality of policy implementation begins with the technical and managerial skills of the implementing staff. Their domain knowledge, procedural skills, and managerial abilities (such as planning, control, and monitoring) are critical in determining whether policies can be implemented as intended or whether they become distorted in practice.

- **Political Support and External Relations**

Internal and external characteristics also determine the success of implementation, particularly the level of political support received by the implementing agency. Agencies that have strong ties to the national political elite, government officials in other organizations, and client groups are typically better able to secure resources, policy space, and protection from negative interventions, making it easier for them to implement policies consistently

- **Quality Of Internal Communication and Leadership**

The nature and quality of internal communication within an agency are critical to ensuring a unified approach to policy implementation. Policies are unlikely to succeed if information does not flow vertically (top-down) and horizontally (across workgroups), or if key actors have differing understandings of the policy's objectives and procedures.

- **Staff Commitment and the Location of the Bureaucracy**

The success of a policy also depends heavily on the level of acceptance and commitment to the policy's objectives among implementation staff (Sager & Gofen, 2022). If staff merely carry out the policy as an administrative routine without understanding or believing in its objectives, implementation will tend to be formalistic and fail to bring about tangible change

Figure 1: Determinants Of Successful Decentralization Policy Implementation.

Source: Cheema And Rondinelli (1983: 28)

3. METHODS

The focus of this study is the implementation of

the division of authority between the central government and local governments, as well as the dynamics of civil registration services through various policies that have been issued. To analyze this topic, the author employs a qualitative approach, given that the research subject is complex and dynamic, and the author aims to gain an in-depth understanding of the situation and conditions and identify patterns.

In selecting research informants/respondents, the author employed a purposive sampling technique. The research object in this study is the dynamics of the implementation of Population Administration as an authority delegated by the Central Government to the Bandung Regency Local Government, particularly following the enactment of Law No. 24 of 2013. Data collection techniques utilized observation and interviews for primary data, while secondary data were sourced from activity reports, regulations, and other relevant documents.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1. *Implementation Of Population Administration Decentralization Policy in Bandung Regency In 2024*

A. *Environmental Conditions*

The successful implementation of civil registration policies requires support from *the political structure, the policy-making process, the local power structure, sociocultural factors, organizations of program beneficiaries, and the adequacy of physical infrastructure.*

1. *Political Structure*

In the context of state governance, the political structure is reflected in the commitment to protect and recognize the legal status of all citizens through the enactment of Law No. 23 of 2006 and its implementing regulations. Indeed, Population Administration now serves as the backbone for all services based on the National Identification Number (NIK) within the framework of Population Administration. In the implementation of decentralization policies, particularly Population Administration in Bandung Regency.

In accordance with the provisions of Law No. 23 of 2014, the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) is a component of the regional government administration alongside the Regional Head. This means that every policy, regional regulation, and budget must be discussed jointly by the Regional Head and the DPRD. The process of discussing regulations between the executive and

legislative branches is a political process aimed at reconciling the technocratic interests of the executive with the political interests represented by the members of the DPRD.

In the context of Bandung Regency, commitment and synergy between the executive and legislative branches have been established for pro-people programs; however, one of the challenges faced stems from the categorization of government affairs delegated to Bandung Regency. Government affairs related to Population Administration and Civil Registration are not included in the Mandatory Affairs related to basic services, even though they form the foundation of those services. Consequently, the government has not established Minimum Service Standards (SPM) that can be used as a priority consideration in planning and budgeting policies.

Furthermore, at the technical level, any discussion involving the Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*) consistently receives support from commission partners as well as Regional Legislative Council (DPRD) members in general. This situation indicates that the commitment of the executive and legislative branches in Bandung Regency towards the administration of civil registration is quite adequate; however, from the perspective of central government policy, this commitment remains constrained by regulations that classify administrative affairs as mandatory responsibilities unrelated to basic services, so that in terms of budget allocation, it is constrained by regulations requiring every region to prioritize the implementation of Mandatory Affairs related to Basic Services in accordance with the standards set forth in Presidential Regulation No. 2 of 2018 on Minimum Service Standards.

2. *The Policy-Making Process*

Cheema and Rondinelli view decision-making as the core of decentralization, specifically how each level of the system or government is granted the authority to determine and formulate decisions and policies. The implementation of Population Administration following the enactment of Law No. 23 of 2006 and Law No. 24 of 2013 has designated the Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*) as the implementing agency in the Population Administration process. To expand service coverage and optimize service delivery, *Disdukcapil* must be able to formulate policies that address the various potentials and emerging issues across each region and segment of society.

One of the key phases in policy formulation is the

identification of problems and opportunities. The quality of policy formulation depends on the accuracy of this identification. This aligns with the view expressed by Hogwood and Gunn (1984:67) that *“the potential contribution that analysis can make at later stages of the policy process depends on when and how a potential public policy problem or opportunity is initially identified.”*

In the context of administering population administration and civil registration affairs, the Bandung Regency Government has issued several regulations, both policy-

based and technical. Some of these regulations were drafted as guidelines to fill regulatory gaps left by the central government. Regulations issued by both the central government and the Bandung Regency government are considered to have disregarded the local wisdom of each region, which varies socio-culturally. For example, regarding the requirements and procedures for civil registration services, which currently do not require a referral from the RT or RW heads, this makes the service easier on one hand but weaker in terms of oversight on the other.

According to Law No. 25 of 2009 about Public Service, public service providers are obligated, among other things, to deliver quality services in accordance with the principles of public service delivery. However, in the delivery of civil registration services, the optimization of public services is often hindered by limited authority at the regional level.

3. *The Structure of Political Power at the Local Level*

The local power structure plays a crucial role in efforts to encourage the community to comply with civil registration regulations. Village heads, neighborhood chiefs, community leaders, and religious leaders are expected to educate the public and explain the importance of civil registration documents in daily life. The significance of the local power structure is also shaped by the underlying understanding that informs perspectives and actions. To enhance the knowledge and understanding of local leaders, intensive outreach and awareness campaigns are necessary.

Within the community, there are also local political structures that have developed and influence public opinion in general, such as Neighborhood Associations (*Rukun Tetangga*), Community Associations (*Rukun Warga*), Village Councils (BPD), and Village Development Councils (LPMD). In public service delivery policies, their

roles have been minimized to streamline bureaucratic procedures. However, in some areas of Bandung Regency, certain service channels still require verification by these structures.

4. *Sociocultural Conditions*

Based on interviews with informants, several sociocultural factors exist in the community of Bandung Regency, including early marriage. According to data from the Bandung Regency Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs for 2024, out of a total of 26.374 marriages, 1,6% occurred among individuals under the age of 19, and thus could not be officially registered. Marriages that are not officially registered by the state will hinder the issuance of civil registration documents and access to other public services.

In some areas of Bandung Regency, residents still do not take the importance of having up-to-date identification documents seriously; they only apply for them when necessary to access other public services, such as hospitals, schools, or banks. The data used is also frequently inconsistent, leading to chaos in the records maintained by public service agencies.

5. *Beneficiary Organizations/Institutions*

Organizations receiving program support in the implementation of civil registration policies (Organizations of program beneficiaries) – in addition to those with formal structures – the success of decentralization in the civil registration sector must also be supported by informal organizations, which serve as key actors capable of assisting local governments in educating the public about the importance of proper civil registration.

Based on the findings, in Bandung Regency there are organizations with structures extending down to the village/sub-district level, including the Family Welfare Empowerment Movement Team (TP PKK), Karang Taruna, the Indonesian National Youth Committee (KNPI), the Indonesian Midwives Association (IBI), and other institutions. To enhance campaigns and public outreach, the Population and Civil Registration Office have established partnerships with various institutions and organizations, such as the TP PKK.

6. *Adequacy Of Physical Infrastructure*

The implementation of civil registration policies must be supported by adequate physical infrastructure in line with the service targets to be achieved, specifically office buildings that meet service standards. Based on observations, the Civil

Registration and Population Agency currently have two office buildings: a service building that is combined with workspaces, and an auditorium building that is combined with an archive room. The buildings were constructed in 1992 and are currently inadequate to accommodate all staff and the equipment housed within them; as the buildings age, their quality has begun to deteriorate. According to evaluations by the Regional Disaster Management Agency and the Fire and Rescue Department, the *Disdukcapil* buildings are not yet equipped with

disaster preparedness facilities.

B. Interorganizational Factors

7. Clarity And Consistency of Program Objectives and Appropriate Division of Tasks

Based on the results of interviews and field observations, the organizational structure of the *Disdukcapil* has been designed to accommodate the details of the authorities mandated in the annex to Law No. 23 of 2014, with the following mapping:

Table 1: Mapping Of *Disdukcapil* Functions.

No	Regional Authority	Responsible Division
1	Population Registration Services	Population Registration Services Division
2	Civil Registration Services	Civil Registration Services Division
3	a. Collection of Population Data b. Utilization and presentation of district/city population databases	Population Administration Information Management Division
4	Preparation of District/City Population Profiles	Service Innovation Data Management Division

Source: Regent Regulation No. 1 Of 2022.

The established structure is already capable of carrying out its mandated duties; however, a challenge arises regarding the alignment of programs with institutional frameworks following the issuance of the Minister of Home Affairs' Decision No. 050-3708 of 2020 on the Results of Verification and Validation of Updates to Clarifications, Codification, and Nomenclature of Regional Development and Financial Planning, which differs from the mapping of duties and functions, resulting in activities being conducted across different sectors. This situation complicates coordination patterns, particularly regarding budgetary structure policies and the implementation of activities that differ from the framework of core duties and functions.

In accordance with the provisions of Law No. 23 of 2006 and Law No. 24 of 2013, and taking into account geographical and demographic factors, the Bandung Regency

Government should have established Technical Implementation Units under the Population and Civil Registration Office (UPT *Disdukcapil*). However, given the limited availability of administrative personnel and budget, services are currently provided at the *Disdukcapil* Office, with operators assigned to 31 (thirty-one) sub-districts and the appointment of 270 Village Registration Officers and 10 Sub-district Registration Officers; meanwhile, the position of Civil Registration Officer remains held by the Head of *Disdukcapil*.

Based on the results of the observation, given the vast size of Bandung Regency, service stations

should be established at several locations located far from the regency capital and sub-district capitals. Difficult access to civil registration services can be exploited by unscrupulous parties who offer services to process civil registration documents in exchange for money.

8. Effective Planning, Budgeting, And Implementation Procedures

The planning, budgeting, and implementation procedures for the implementation of Population Administration policies in Bandung Regency, as indicated by interviews with informants, have been carried out effectively in accordance with planning documents that reference the RPJMD and RKPD. In the exercise of authority over Population Administration and Civil Registration, one of the guiding documents is the RPJMD and RKPD, the preparation of which is coordinated by the Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda). Based on these documents, the Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*), as a regional agency, prepares the Strategic Plan (Renstra) and Work Plan (Renja). One of the strategic issues identified relates to the limited authority of *Disdukcapil* in carrying out government affairs regarding Population Administration and Civil Registration.

9. The Quality of Communication Between Organizations and the Effectiveness of Interorganizational Connectivity

In the administration of local government, the

Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*) maintain communication with parties involved in service delivery, both within local government agencies and with other institutions outside the local government. *Disdukcapil* is part of several working groups at the local government level, such as the Regional Poverty Alleviation Team (TPKD) and the Local Government Performance Report (LPPD) Compilation Team. Furthermore, based on observations, *Disdukcapil* also plays a role in efforts to address and reduce the prevalence of stunting and in reconciling data on the receipt of various forms of assistance provided by the local government. *Disdukcapil*'s involvement in these task forces relates to the availability of aggregate data it possesses and the provision of civil registration services, which can be carried out through a territorial approach requiring special attention. Meanwhile, coordination and communication with agencies outside the local government are conducted by *Disdukcapil*, for example with the Religious Courts and the Ministry of Religious Affairs within the framework of service cooperation.

C. The Role of Natural Resources in the Implementation of Decentralization Policies

a. Control Over Finances

Within the local government financial management structure, the Head of the Population and Civil Registration Office serves as the Budget User, in accordance with Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation No. 77 of 2022 on Technical Guidelines for Local Government Financial Management. Based on interview findings, control over local government finances is currently easier because all local government financial management must utilize the SIPD system. Subsequently, the budget is reviewed by the Government Internal Oversight Agency (APIP)—specifically the Inspectorate and the State Audit Board (BPKP)—to ensure alignment with planning indicators. At the conclusion of activities, an evaluation is conducted by the Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda) and the Inspectorate based on financial management performance and the level of compliance with applicable laws and regulations. So far, financial controls have been carried out effectively; one proof of this is that the Bandung Regency Government has received an Unqualified Opinion (WTP) from the Indonesian Audit Board (BPK RI) on its Regional Financial Report.

b. Adequacy/Suitability of Budgeting and Availability of Budgetary Resources

Based on interviews, information gathered, and field observations, it appears that the availability of the Regional Budget (APBD) remains limited. The *Disdukcapil* budget only ensures that routine services operate normally; however, efforts to optimize or improve the quality and scope of services seem difficult to achieve. *Disdukcapil* is often regarded as a specialized agency (*lex specialist*), yet this designation is not always accompanied by adequate budgetary support. Based on this, it can be concluded that the adequacy of the budget for implementing Population Administration policies in Bandung Regency remains limited. According to the APBD Formulation Guidelines, every region—including Bandung Regency—must prioritize programs/activities related to mandatory basic services, guided by the SPM (Standard of Minimum Performance) established by the central government. Although Population Administration affairs are not included in these mandatory services, the Regent of Bandung has shown significant attention to this matter, as evidenced by the policy of gradually purchasing ADM machines to be placed in every village/subdistrict office. Furthermore, Population Administration affairs are also not included in mandatory activities, meaning activities whose budget percentages are mandated by the Central Government.

c. Support From National and Local Policymakers and the National Bureaucracy

The Government of Indonesia has issued Presidential Regulation No. 62 of 2019 on the National Strategy for Accelerating Population Administration for the Development of Vital Statistics, which outlines a set of strategies aimed at accelerating the issuance of population documents to ensure the legal status and legal certainty of Indonesian citizens.

The Indonesian government has also issued Presidential Regulation No. 82 of 2023 on the Acceleration of Digital Transformation and the Integration of National Digital Services, which, among other things, mandates the development of Priority SPBE applications to support civil registration services based on the Digital Population Identity (IKD). These policies serve to strengthen the implementation of civil registration in the regions. Furthermore, regarding support for the Population Administration program, the Central Government, through the Ministry of Home Affairs, periodically mandates budgeting policies by local governments in accordance with the provisions of Government Regulation No. 12 of 2019 on Regional Financial

Management.

D. Characteristics Of Implementing Agencies

a. Technical, Managerial, And Political Skills Related to the Capacity to Coordinate, Control, And Integrate Decisions from Sub-Units

Currently, civil registration services are conducted online via the SIAK system, which is supported by a closed-network communication infrastructure known as the Data Communication Network (*Jarkomdat*) from the Directorate General of Civil Registration and Population. At the technical level, the required skills include proficiency in operating computers using SIAK applications, computer networking systems, database management, and information security management systems. Based on interview results, the majority of functional officials at the Population and Civil Registration Office have a background in Information Technology, so they already possess the basic and technical understanding of network and database configuration.

Next, regarding managerial competencies, in the administration of civil registration, the competencies

required of *Disdukcapil* officials are stipulated in Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation No. 60 of 2021 concerning the Appointment, Dismissal, and Performance Evaluation of Senior Executive Officials, Administrative Officials, and Supervisory Officials at *Disdukcapil*.

This means that, in general, every structural official at the Population and Civil Registration Office has undergone a verification process by the Directorate General of Population and Civil Registration, as outlined in Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation No. 60 of 2021. Furthermore, based on the results of a review of personnel data at the *Disdukcapil*, all structural officials at the *Disdukcapil* have completed leadership training to meet managerial competencies in accordance with the mandate of Law No. 20 of 2023 on the Civil Service. Furthermore, regarding managerial competencies and skills, structural officials at the Population and Civil Registration Office must also be able to coordinate, manage, and integrate various potentials and emerging issues arising from field services to formulate various innovation strategies.

Based on observations and interviews, the Population and Civil Registration Office have initiated various innovations to optimize services, including:

Table 2: Innovations At the Population and Civil Registration Office of Bandung Regency.

No	Type of Innovation	Description
1	KUE LAPIS (Visits to the Elderly and People with Disabilities)	Outreach services for elderly residents and people with disabilities who are unable and unable to come to the village/subdistrict office
2	CEMARA DESA (Self-Service Printing in Subdistricts and Villages)	Self-service printing of civil registration documents using ADM machines available at village/subdistrict offices
3	PELAMINAN CANTIK (Post-Marriage Validation Population Administration Services)	Service for updating marital status data recorded on the Family Card and registering a child's birth certificate following the issuance of a marriage validation decree by the Religious Affairs Office
4	LENTERA BEDAS (Integrated Population Administration and Education Service)	Outreach and Education Services on Civil Registration, followed by integrated delivery of all civil registration services specifically in areas classified as poverty pockets within Bandung Regency
5	SI CAKAR SAKTI (System for Printing Family Cards and Certificates at Hospitals)	Services provided at the Regional General Hospital to the public: if a child is born at the hospital, the family will receive a Birth Certificate, Family Card, and KIA; if a death occurs, a Death Certificate will be issued and the Family Card updated)

Source: *Disdukcapil*, 2024

In general, technical, managerial, and political skills are already strong; however, the Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*), as the implementing agency, must continue to conduct periodic self-assessments of these skills to inform capacity-building efforts, given the ever-evolving dynamics of service delivery and information technology systems.

b. Resources And Political Support

Public policy at the local level represents the political vision of local leaders, which originates from

political aspirations and dynamics and is subsequently formulated into formal public policy. Robert Eyestone, as cited in Agustino (2008:6), defines public policy as the relationship between a government unit and its environment. In the implementation of Population Administration in Bandung Regency, political support from the legislature is already in place, as evidenced by budgetary and policy support; however, the actualization of the budget remains limited due to constraints related to priority levels and budget availability.

c. Effectiveness Of Internal Communication

Based on observations, internal communication at the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registration Office has been conducted through weekly routine morning assemblies, which are led on a rotating basis by the head of the office, the secretary, and the division heads as a means to inform staff about general service issues. Additionally, technical evaluation meetings are held regularly, led by the head of the office or the secretary, to monitor the progress of activities and address various obstacles and challenges encountered. Meanwhile, to involve all components, the Population and Civil Registration Office hold gatherings, albeit with limited frequency. In general, the internal communication process has been carried out periodically, although it is limited in scope to structural and functional officials.

d. The Level of Proximity Between the Implementing Agency and Beneficiary Organizations, As Well As the Relationship with Beneficiary Organizations.

The Population and Civil Registration Office of Bandung Regency have routinely developed Service Standards in accordance with Ministry of State Apparatus and Regional Government Regulation No. 15 of 2014 on Guidelines for Service Standards and the Public Satisfaction Survey (SKM) in accordance with Ministry of State Apparatus and Regional Government Regulation No. 16 of 2014 on Guidelines for the Public Satisfaction Survey regarding Public Service Providers, with community involvement. The formulation of Service Standards covers all services organized through the Public Consultation Forum mechanism; Service Standards that have been discussed with the public are subsequently established by a Decision of the Head of the Population and Civil Registration Office.

Furthermore, regarding the Service Quality Index (SKM), the latest survey data on nine indicators—namely requirements, procedures, service time, costs/fees, service specifications, service competence, staff behavior, service information, and complaint handling, suggestions, and feedback, show a consistent trend: 2024 with a score of 88.54 (A), 2023 with a score of 85.40 (A), 2022 with a score of 88.38 (A), and 2021 with a score of 88.32 (A) (Bandung Regency LAKIP, 2024, 2023, 2022, and 2021).

e. Quality Of Leadership in Implementing Agencies

The Minister of Home Affairs' Decision on Technical Guidelines for the Performance Evaluation of Department Heads and Department Secretaries at the Population and Civil Registration Offices in Provinces and Regencies/Cities is a regulation issued annually on a temporary basis for evaluation purposes. In the first semester of 2024, the Population and Civil Registration Office of Bandung Regency received a "Good" rating with a score of 87.37.

In providing civil registration services, the Civil Registration and Population Agency (*Disdukcapil*) have established several working partnerships with sub-district heads, village heads, and other local government officials. Additionally, *Disdukcapil* officials must be able to manage and foster commitment among staff—most of whom are non-civil servants—to achieve shared goals.

f. Commitment Of Employees/Staff to the Implementing Agency's Programs

In the delivery of civil registration services, civil registration officers serve as the frontline of service, interacting directly with the public. Their role is crucial to the quality and speed of service delivery. Therefore, a strong commitment is required from all civil registration officers to provide high-quality services.

The workforce composition at the Bandung Regency Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*), particularly among civil registration operators, is dominated by daily wage workers (PHL), whose average wages remain below the Regional Minimum Wage (UMR). However, based on interviews and field observations, it was found that in the implementation of Population Administration at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Bandung Regency, in general, all staff members demonstrate a strong commitment, although there are still some employees who exploit loopholes in the service system to engage in actions that do not comply with regulations.

g. Location Of the Implementing Agency Within the Administrative System

Regional agencies serve as *the operational core*, assisting the regional head in carrying out governmental affairs that fall under the authority of the region, including both mandatory and optional responsibilities.

Figure 2: The Five Basic Parts of Organizations.

Source: Henry Mintzberg (1979).

The Population and Civil Registration Agency (*Disdukcapil*) are considered a specialized institution; the central government has issued *lex specialist* regulations concerning its institutional structure and personnel, such as Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation No. 14 of 2020 on Guidelines for the Nomenclature of Population and Civil Registration Agencies in Provinces and Regencies/Cities, along with highly detailed technical regulations. These policies have positioned government affairs as a decentralized policy with a decentralized feel, subject to various strict regulations from the central government. These policies place *Disdukcapil* in two distinct roles: on one hand, as a regional apparatus assisting the regional head, and on the other, as an agent of the central government.

5. THEORETICAL FINDINGS

Researchers concluded that budgetary and human resource factors pose challenges in the implementation of this policy. This stems from inconsistencies in defining the concept of decentralization within the scope of Population Administration and Civil Registration, as well as disparities in authority among the central government, the provincial government, and the Bandung Regency government.

The research findings described above led the researchers to recommend a concept for the administration of civil registration—both locally in Bandung Regency and in relation to the concept of decentralization for civil registration affairs—as an

effort to strengthen services and address the shortcomings that currently constitute an ongoing problem.

Decentralization is implemented using an **Adaptive Decentralization** approach based on Efficiency, Accountability, and Externalities, while still taking national strategic interests into account.

The framework is as follows:

1. The decentralization of civil registration authority is divided into three tiers: national strategy (the Central Government, specifically the Director General of Civil Registration and Population), operational strategy (Provincial Governments), and technical operations (Regency/Municipal Governments)
2. The central government carries out its national strategic role by formulating general policies as a roadmap for the development of the Population Administration at the national level. To ensure that the roadmap is properly implemented, the central government, through the Ministry of Home Affairs, conducts monitoring and evaluation using the Norms, Standards, Procedures, and Criteria (NSPK) framework;
3. Strategic authorities of a tactical nature may be delegated to the Provincial Population and Civil Registration Office, along with the relevant budgetary policies and resources. This will strengthen the role of West Java Province as an extension of the Central Government; the regulatory mechanisms that may be employed

include Decentralization or Assistance Tasks.

4. Operational authority is exercised by the District/Municipal *Disdukcapil* as the implementing agency.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results outlined above, the implementation of the Population Administration decentralization policy in Bandung Regency can be summarized as follows:

1. Environmental factors and their associated sub-factors have been addressed, but recurring issues remain, including decision-making processes that tend to be ineffective, limited facilities and infrastructure, and a scope of cooperation that remains limited due to the lengthy approval process for cooperation agreements, which must go through the central government.
2. The factor of inter-organizational relations and its associated sub-factors are in place; however, there are issues regarding the mapping of functions in relation to compliance with Ministry of Home Affairs Regulation No. 050-

3708 of 2020. The Population and Civil Registration Office of Bandung Regency has also not yet established a Population and Civil Registration Field Office (UPT) as mandated by Law No. 24 of 2013 to improve the scope of service delivery.

3. The resources for policy implementation and their associated sub-factors remain inadequate and need to be improved, given the service workload in Bandung Regency. Local policymakers support the civil registration program by providing budgetary support, although they have not yet been able to deliver optimal services.
4. The characteristic factors of implementing agencies and their associated sub-factors largely need to be improved. The Population and Civil Registration Office (*Disdukcapil*) is a regional agency assisting the regent as the head of the region in carrying out decentralized functions; however, some policies still have a deconcentration-oriented nature, resulting in many service-related issues that cannot be resolved at the regional level.

REFERENCES

- Cheema, G.S. and Rondinelli, D.A. (1983). DECENTRALIZATION and DEVELOPMENT: Creswell, J.W. (2010). RESEARCH DESIGN: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. Third Edition (Translated by Achmad Fawaid). PUSTAKA PELAJAR.
- Creswell, John W. and Creswell, J. David (2018). RESEARCH DESIGN: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. Fifth Edition. SAGE Publications.
- Edwards III, G. C (1980). IMPLEMENTING PUBLIC POLICY. Congressional Quarterly Press. Kantaprawira, Rusadi (2004). The Political System in Indonesia. Sinar Baru Algensindo.
- Government Regulation No. 40 of 2009 on Implementation Guidelines for Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration, as amended by Law No. 24 of 2013 on Amendments to Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration.
- Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration, as amended by Law No. 24 of 2013 on Amendments to Law No. 23 of 2006 on Population Administration.
- Law No. 23 of 2014 on Regional Government.
- Mahfud, MD (2004). Legal Politics in Indonesia. LP3S.
- Mansien, A. P. (2020). Issues Regarding Administrative Authority in Population Management under Government Regulation No. 40 of 2019. *Nahkoda: Journal of Public Administration*, 19(2), 128–150.
- Meriem, Merselab (2025). The Mintzberg Model of Organizational Configurations: An Analytical Study of the Theoretical Foundations. *International Journal of Innovative Technologies in Economy*, 2(5), [https://doi.org/10.31435/ijite.2\(50\).2025.3321](https://doi.org/10.31435/ijite.2(50).2025.3321)
- Mintzberg, Henry (1979). THE STRUCTURING OF ORGANIZATIONS. Prentice-Hall.
- Policy Implementation in Developing Countries. SAGE PUBLICATIONS.
- Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 77 of 2022 on Technical Guidelines for Regional Financial Management.
- Regulation of the Regent of Bandung No. 84 of 2016 on the Duties, Functions, and Operational Procedures of the Population and Civil Registration Office.
- Smith, B.C. (1985). DECENTRALIZATION: The Territorial Dimension of the State. George Allen & Unwin.